

Synthesis of protein in soybean with sulphur-phosphorus nutrition

A. K. Dwivedi* and P. N. Bapat

Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, J. N. Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur-482 004, India

Manuscript received 17 March 1998, revised 8 December 1998, accepted 10 February 1999

The influence of fertilizer phosphorus and sulphur on protein synthesis in soybean grown on sulphur and phosphorus deficient vertisol has been evaluated. The protein synthesis in soybean grain is suppressed at low levels with a concomitant increase in the accumulation of undesirable non-protein nitrogenous (NPN) compounds. Amongst NPN, the amino acid-N decline significantly from control to 50 kg ha⁻¹ dose of S and P₂O₅. Contribution of phosphorus to the protein synthesis follows similar trend. However, the effect of P in reducing the NPN content is less spectacular as compared to that of sulphur.

Under intensified cropping systems the use of high analysis sulphur-free fertilizers for the nutrition of high yielding varieties results in severe deficiency of sulphur in soils. However, sulphur nutrition has long been known to have a close relationship with the nitrogen metabolism in plants¹⁻³. It has been widely accepted that S and P have a close synergistic relationship with protein metabolism⁴. Keeping this in view, a study was undertaken to investigate the effect of S and P fertilizer application on the protein metabolism in soybean.

Results and Discussion

Total-N and protein-N content : The total-N and protein-N (Table 1) were significantly increased by the S

and P application upto 50 kg ha⁻¹ dose. Several authors¹⁻⁵ reported similar effect due to increase in nitrogen fixation capacity. The maximum protein-N content was obtained at S and P 50 kg dose. Increase in protein-N ranged from 3.20% without S and P to 7.21% at S and P 50 kg dose. However, with increase in S level protein-N formed a greater proportion of the total-N in the plant.

As discussed above, the protein content decreased at low S dose due to accumulation of non protein-N. Therefore, under such conditions the procedure of using crude protein (total-N × 6.25) as a criterion of crop quality may lead to erroneous results².

Table 1. Effect of S and P levels on nitrogenous fractions in soybean

Sulphur level (Kg S ha ⁻¹)	Phosphorus level (kg P ₂ O ₅ ha ⁻¹)				Mean	Cd 5%
	0	25	50	75		
Total N (%)						
0	3.73	3.94	4.61	4.87	4.28	S 0.16
25	3.75	4.87	5.07	5.12	4.70	P 0.16
50	5.02	6.60	7.57	7.51	6.67	SXP 0.33
75	5.06	6.69	7.52	7.53	6.70	
Mean	4.39	5.59	6.20	6.27	-	
Protein N (%)						
0	3.20	3.42	4.13	4.40	3.78	S 0.22
25	3.26	4.40	4.63	4.70	4.25	P 0.22
50	4.58	6.19	7.21	7.15	6.28	SXP 0.45
75	4.64	6.29	7.15	7.17	6.31	
Mean	3.92	5.07	5.78	5.85	-	
Non protein N (%)						
0	0.53	0.52	0.48	0.47	0.50	S 0.006
25	0.49	0.47	0.44	0.42	0.45	P 0.006
50	0.44	0.41	0.36	0.36	0.39	SXP 0.120
75	0.42	0.40	0.37	0.36	0.39	
Mean	0.47	0.45	0.41	0.40	-	
Nitrate-N (mg/100 g)						
0	58	56	53	52	54	S 1.02
25	49	46	45	39	44	P 1.02
50	38	34	28	27	31	SXP 2.05
75	34	30	27	26	29	
Mean	45	41	38	36	-	

Table-1 (contd.)

		Ammoniacal-N (mg/100 g)				
0	76	73	70	70	72	S 1.36
25	73	67	56	54	62	P 1.36
50	58	49	44	43	48	SXP 2.71
75	49	47	45	44	46	
Mean	64	59	54	52	-	
		Amide-N (mg/100 g)				
0	150	144	142	138	143	S 2.91
25	141	137	131	128	134	P 2.91
50	128	120	106	109	116	SXP 5.81
75	125	118	110	109	115	
Mean	136	130	123	121	-	
		Amino acid N (mg/100 g)				
0	250	244	218	211	231	S 3.62
25	226	220	212	196	213	P 3.62
50	210	204	183	185	195	SXP 7.24
75	209	201	186	184	195	
Mean	224	217	200	194	-	

Non-protein-N content : The impact of sulphur on protein formation is impressive, indicating clearly the tendency of the plants to accumulate non-protein-N in case of S-deficient soils. In the present study, all the non-protein-N fractions (nitrate, ammoniacal, amide and amino acid-N) significantly decreased with successive application of S (Table 1). Among the non-protein-N fractions, the major fraction consisted of amino acid-N and amide-N followed by ammoniacal-N and nitrate-N. Greater accumulation of organic form of NPN over inorganic form could be due to enhanced incorporation of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ into organic form², at the same time, reduced synthesis of protein from amino acids under low sulphur conditions^{2,3,6}. Similarly, phosphorus also decreased the NPN fractions, indicating thereby, the precursors implicated for the amino acids are restricted at amide stage only under low P supply^{2,6}.

The study indicates that sulphur deficiency is increased in the soils and may become a limiting input in crop production. Under such conditions, inclusion of sulphur in fertilizer schedule is a must to avoid low productivity and quality, specially for protein and oil-rich crop like soybean.

Experimental

A green-hosue experiment was conducted on a clayey

soil (Typic Chromustert) low in available phosphorus ($12.6 \text{ kg P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ ha}^{-1}$) and S ($14.4 \text{ kg S ha}^{-1}$) with pH 7.4, electrical conductivity 0.2 dS m^{-1} and organic carbon 0.4%. Four level of phosphorus and sulphur (0, 25, 50 and 75 $\text{kg P}_2\text{O}_5$ and S ha^{-1}) were applied through Na_2HPO_4 and $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively, in a factorial R.B.D., with three replications. A basal dose of 20 kg ha^{-1} N (urea) and K_2O (muriate of potash) was also applied uniformly. The soybean (variety Gaurav) was grown till harvest. Grain samples were dried at 55° for 16 h. Nitrogen fractions (total and protein-N, nitrate-N, ammoniacal-N, amide-N, amino acid-N) were determined⁸.

References

1. W. H. Allaway and J. F. Thompson, *Soil Sci.*, 1986, **101**, 240.
2. P. N. Bapat and S. B. Sinha, *Bull. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1984, **13**, 356.
3. H. L. S. Tandon, *Sulphur Agric.*, 1992, **16**, 20.
4. A. K. Dwivedi, S. B. Sinha and J. P. Mahajan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 166.
5. P. K. Agrawal and O. P. Vyas, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1974, **44**, 652.
6. K. N. Tiwari, *Sulphur Agric.*, 1990, **14**, 29.
7. "Official Methods of Analysis of the Association of Official Agricultural Chemists", A.O.A.C., Washington, D.C., 1965.
8. S. A. Stewart and L. K. Porter, *Agron. J.*, 1969, **61**, 267.